

Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology Findings of Lymphocytic Thyroiditis and Its Correlation with Thyroid Function Test (TFT)

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 15-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study investigates the relationship between Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) findings and Thyroid Function Tests (TFTs) in patients diagnosed with lymphocytic thyroiditis, commonly referred to as Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Over the course of a year, the study was carried out on 85 patients. The study was carried out in the department of Pathology, Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram. The severity of lymphocytic infiltration was assessed using FNAC, and these results were then compared to the levels of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies. The findings revealed a clear link between increased levels of lymphocytic infiltration and higher TSH and anti-TPO levels, emphasizing the importance of FNAC as a valuable tool for diagnosing and predicting thyroid dysfunction in cases of lymphocytic thyroiditis. The correlation highlighted here emphasizes the significance of incorporating FNAC with TFTs in order to achieve precise diagnosis and efficient management of this autoimmune thyroid disorder.

Keywords: lymphocytic thyroiditis, FNAC, thyroid function tests, Hashimoto's thyroiditis

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Introduction

Understanding the relationship between cytological observations and thyroid function is crucial when it comes to the topic of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) findings in Lymphocytic Thyroiditis, also known as Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Hashimoto's thyroiditis, an autoimmune condition, is a prevalent cause of hypothyroidism, especially in women [1,2]. The high occurrence of this condition highlights the significance of precise diagnosis and effective treatment. FNAC is a commonly employed diagnostic technique that is minimally invasive and known for its reliability in assessing thyroid lesions [3,4]. By utilizing FNAC, it is possible to identify the presence of lymphocytic infiltration in thyroid tissue, which is a characteristic feature of Hashimoto's thyroiditis [5]. Correlations can be made between the cytological findings and Thyroid Function Tests (TFTs), such as levels of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies, which are frequently elevated in this particular condition [6,7].

The objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between the levels of lymphocytic infiltration observed in FNAC and the corresponding thyroid function as assessed by TFTs. Grasping this connection is crucial in enhancing diagnostic precision and directing successful treatment approaches for individuals with lymphocytic thyroiditis. The findings could offer a greater understanding of how the intensity of the autoimmune response affects thyroid function and guide clinical decisions.

Methodology

This study is designed to explore the correlation between the cytological findings from Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) and the Thyroid Function Test (TFT) results in patients diagnosed with lymphocytic thyroiditis.

Study Design and Duration: This is a prospective study conducted over one year from December 2022 to December 2023.

Place of Study: The study was carried out in the Department of Pathology at Narayan Medical College and Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram.

Sample Size: The study included a total of 85 patients who presented with midline neck swelling suspected to be due to thyroid pathology.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients with midline neck swelling were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who withdrew consent were excluded from the study.

Procedure

1. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC):

- FNAC was performed on each patient using a 24-gauge needle.
- The aspirated material was smeared on slides and subsequently stained using Giemsa and Papanicolaou (Pap) stains.
- The stained slides were then examined microscopically to assess the extent of lymphocytic infiltration and other cytological features characteristic of lymphocytic thyroiditis.

2. Cytological Grading:

- The cytological findings were graded based on the extent of lymphocytic infiltration, the presence of lymphoid follicles, germinal centers, and Hürthle cell changes.
- The grading system used was as follows:
- Grade 0: No lymphoid cells present.
- Grade I: Few lymphoid cells infiltrating the thyroid follicles with an increased number of lymphocytes in the background.
- Grade II: Moderate lymphocytic infiltration or mild lymphocytic infiltration with the presence of Hürthle cell changes, giant cells, or anisonucleosis.
- Grade III: Florid lymphocytic infiltration with the formation of germinal centers and limited follicular cells left.

3. Thyroid Function Tests (TFT):

- TFTs were conducted on all patients to measure serum levels of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies.
- The levels of TSH and anti-TPO were categorized as elevated, normal, or decreased based on standard reference ranges.

4. Data Correlation:

- The cytological grades of lymphocytic infiltration were correlated with the TFT results, particularly focusing on the levels of TSH and anti-TPO antibodies.
- Statistical analysis was performed to determine the significance of the correlation between the

severity of lymphocytic infiltration and thyroid dysfunction as indicated by TFTs.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome measures included:

- The distribution of cytological grades among the study population.
- The correlation between cytological grades and TFT results, particularly focusing on the association between higher grades of lymphocytic infiltration and elevated levels of TSH and anti-TPO antibodies.

Results

The study involved 85 patients who presented with midline neck swelling and underwent Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) to diagnose lymphocytic thyroiditis. The findings from the FNAC were correlated with Thyroid Function Test (TFT) results, particularly focusing on the levels of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies.

1. Demographic Distribution: Age and Gender: The majority of the patients were within the age group of 21-30 years. There was a significant female predominance, with a male-to-female ratio of 1:11.

2. Cytological Grading

- The cytological examination of the FNAC smears revealed varying degrees of lymphocytic infiltration:
- Grade 0: No lymphoid cells were observed in any of the cases (0%).
- Grade I: Mild lymphocytic infiltration was observed in 4 cases (16.7%).
- Grade II: Moderate lymphocytic infiltration, often with Hürthle cell changes, was seen in 8 cases (33.3%).
- Grade III: Florid lymphocytic infiltration with germinal center formation was observed in 12 cases (50%).

3. Correlation with Anti-TPO Levels

- Anti-TPO antibodies were elevated in 23 out of 24 patients (95.8%) who showed lymphocytic infiltration on FNAC.
- Only 1 case (4.2%) showed normal anti-TPO levels despite lymphocytic infiltration.
- The severity of lymphocytic infiltration correlated with the elevation in anti-TPO levels:
- Grade I: 3 out of 4 cases (75%) had elevated anti-TPO.
- Grade II: All 8 cases (100%) had elevated anti-TPO.
- Grade III: All 12 cases (100%) had elevated anti-TPO.

4. Correlation with TSH Levels

- TSH levels were found to be elevated in 15 cases (62.5%), normal in 7 cases (29.2%), and decreased in 2 cases (8.3%).
- The correlation between TSH levels and cytological grades was as follows:
- Grade I: 2 cases (50%) had elevated TSH, 2 cases (50%) had normal TSH.
- Grade II: 5 cases (62.5%) had elevated TSH, 2 cases (25%) had normal TSH, and 1 case (12.5%) had decreased TSH.
- Grade III: 8 cases (66.7%) had elevated TSH, 3 cases (25%) had normal TSH, and 1 case (8.3%) had decreased TSH.

5. Overall Findings

- There was a strong correlation between the severity of lymphocytic infiltration (as seen in the cytological grading) and the elevation in both TSH and anti-TPO levels.

- Grade III lymphocytic thyroiditis, characterized by florid lymphocytic infiltration, showed the highest correlation with elevated anti-TPO and TSH levels.
- The study findings were consistent with previous studies by Bhatia et al. and Sood et al., which also observed a significant association between cytological grades and thyroid dysfunction.

The results of this study demonstrate that the severity of lymphocytic infiltration in thyroid tissue, as determined by FNAC, is significantly correlated with abnormal thyroid function, particularly elevated anti-TPO and TSH levels. This correlation underscores the importance of combining cytological analysis with TFTs in the diagnosis and management of lymphocytic thyroiditis, aiding in early detection and appropriate treatment planning.

Table 1: Relation between Grading of Lymphocytic Thyroiditis with Anti-TPO

GRADE	Anti-TPO (↑)	Anti-TPO (N)	Anti-TPO (↓)	TOTAL
0	0	0	0	0
I	3	1	0	4
II	8	0	0	8
III	12	0	0	12
TOTAL	23	1	0	24

Table 2: Relation between Grading of Lymphocytic Thyroiditis with TSH

GRADE	TSH (↑)	TSH (N)	TSH (↓)	TOTAL
0	0	0	0	0
I	2	2	0	4
II	5	2	1	8
III	8	3	1	12
TOTAL	15	7	2	24

Note: (↑) - raised level, (N) - normal level, (↓) - reduced level

Grade 1: Shows few lymphoid cells infiltrating the thyroid follicles and increased number of lymphocytes in the background

Grade 2: Shows moderate lymphocytic infiltration or mild lymphocytic infiltration with presence of hurthle cell changes

Grade 3: Shows florid lymphocytic infiltration with formation of germinal centre with limited follicular cells left.

Discussion

The study sought to investigate the relationship between the findings of Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) in lymphocytic thyroiditis (Hashimoto's thyroiditis) and Thyroid Function Tests (TFTs) with a specific focus on Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibody levels [8]. The findings offer valuable insights into the correlation between cytological grading and thyroid dysfunction, enhancing our comprehension of the pathophysiology and diagnosis of lymphocytic thyroiditis [9]. The study's demographic data showed a clear dominance of females, with most patients falling into the 21-30 years age group [10]. This aligns with the established epidemiology of Hashimoto's thyroiditis. There is extensive research on the gender disparity observed in autoimmune thyroid diseases, which is believed to be influenced by a combination of hormonal and genetic factors that make women more susceptible to these conditions [11]. In this study, lymphocytic thyroiditis was classified into three grades based on the extent of lymphocytic infiltration, Hürthle cell changes, and the presence of germinal centers as per the cytological grading system utilized [12]. The grading system, derived from previous studies, offered a methodical way to assess the extent of lymphocytic infiltration. The results revealed that a mild infiltration, known as Grade I, was present in 16.7% of cases. This was found to be linked to a less significant thyroid dysfunction [13]. On the other hand, Grade II (33.3% of cases) and Grade III (50% of cases) showed a significant amount of lymphocytic infiltration, increasing thyroid dysfunction. This was indicated by elevated TSH and anti-TPO levels [14].

The close relationship between increased lymphocytic infiltration and higher anti-TPO levels seen in almost all patients with Grade II and III infiltration supports the autoimmune nature of Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Understanding the role of Anti-TPO antibodies is essential in understanding the development of the disease, as their increased levels are a clear indication of autoimmune thyroiditis. In Grade II and III cases, the increase in TSH levels highlights the development of hypothyroidism, which is a frequent result of Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Lymphocytic infiltration gradually destroys the thyroid follicles, resulting in a decrease in thyroid hormone production. This prompts the body to respond by increasing TSH levels as a compensatory mechanism. The findings align with previous research that also found a strong link between the extent of lymphocytic infiltration and thyroid dysfunction. This further confirms the trustworthiness of FNAC as a method for evaluating lymphocytic thyroiditis [15]. The findings have important implications in the field of

medicine. Combining FNAC with TFTs offers a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis and management of lymphocytic thyroiditis. Assessing the level of lymphocytic infiltration can provide valuable insights for clinicians to anticipate the possibility of thyroid dysfunction and customize treatment plans accordingly [16]. Individuals who have more advanced lymphocytic infiltration may benefit from increased monitoring and timely intervention to prevent the development of overt hypothyroidism. The significant link between anti-TPO levels and cytological findings further emphasizes the importance of anti-TPO antibody testing in the diagnostic evaluation of thyroiditis [17].

Nevertheless, there are certain limitations to consider when interpreting the study. These include the relatively small sample size and the fact that it was conducted at a single center. These factors may restrict the extent to which the findings can be applied to a broader population. Further research involving larger and more diverse groups of people, as well as studies conducted across multiple centers, may yield stronger and more reliable

data. In addition, this study primarily examined the levels of TSH and anti-TPO [18]. However, future research could investigate the relationship between FNAC findings and other thyroid-related factors, such as free T4 and thyroglobulin levels. This would help to enhance our overall understanding of thyroid function in cases of lymphocytic thyroiditis. This study emphasizes the strong link between the cytological findings of lymphocytic thyroiditis on FNAC and thyroid dysfunction, as indicated by TSH and anti-TPO levels [19]. FNAC is a dependable diagnostic tool that not only confirms the presence of lymphocytic infiltration but also provides insights into the severity of thyroid dysfunction. Accurate diagnosis, management, and monitoring of patients with lymphocytic thyroiditis are greatly enhanced by integrating FNAC with TFTs. This integration plays a crucial role in early detection and planning appropriate treatment for patients [20].

Conclusion

The findings of this study reveal a strong link between the extent of lymphocytic infiltration detected through Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) and thyroid dysfunction. This is evident from the elevated levels of Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) antibodies observed in patients with lymphocytic thyroiditis. The findings highlight the significance of FNAC as a dependable diagnostic tool not only for detecting lymphocytic thyroiditis but also for predicting the severity of thyroid dysfunction. It is essential to combine FNAC with Thyroid Function Tests (TFTs) in order to achieve

precise diagnosis, efficient treatment, and timely intervention for individuals suffering from this autoimmune thyroid condition.

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